

Muslim Organizations and Their Role in Promoting Environmental Conservation

Hina Majid

[Hina.reshi786.rs@manuu.edu.in/](mailto:Hina.reshi786.rs@manuu.edu.in)

Research Scholar (Islamic studies),

Maulana Azad National Urdu University, (ASC)

Budgam, Jammu and Kashmir

ABSTRACT:

Islam is the fastest growing religion in today's world followed by a huge population of over one billion and is practiced virtually in every country of the world. Islam gives practical solution to the problems faced by man in every sphere of life. Islam has given guidelines and solution to the contemporary issues including environmental conservation and its safeguard. Environment protection is an important aspect of Islam. Being Guardians and Khalifah of Allah(SWT) on the Earth, it is the responsibility of Muslims to take care of the environment in a proactive manner. Islam advocates environmental protection and conservation. The articulation of an Islamic environmental ethics in contemporary times is all urgent and need of the hour because Western-style conservation efforts do not fit all cultural and philosophical traditions of the world. The Islamic attitude towards environment and natural resource conservation is not only based on prohibition of over-exploitation but also on sustainable development. The religion of Islam through its teachings and philosophy chalks out the principles for the conservation of environment. The Qur'an through its verses has time and again warned not to be extravagant, to maintain peace and harmony among mankind and with other creations. Similarly there are scores of ahadith by Prophet Muhammad (SAAS) that ordain treating environment & its components with proper care and respect. The world today is facing mounting global environmental challenges of various forms and if these are not taken care of, the future of the earth's ecosystem and the human race will be in danger. Various steps have been taken to mitigate this imminent crisis which may spell doom to the flora and fauna of this planet. Islam being a practice oriented religion offers an opportunity for an effective environment friendly approach that will help in translating environmental protection theory into practical steps as Muslims will consider it as their religious duty and obligation. The Islamic principles stress on the fact that a Muslim is duty bound to take utmost care of the environment and adopt practices that will contribute to sustainability of the environment. Many Muslim Organizations has been set up to counter the problem of environmental degradation. They have been working tirelessly following the principles laid by Quran and Sunnah for the betterment of the environment. They are trying to educate Muslim Communities in the light of Islamic principles so that these communities can bring about the desired change in the lifestyle of people which will result in sustainability and conservation of environment and resources.

Keywords: Environment, Sustainability, Muslim organizations, protection, maintenance.

Introduction

The word *Islam* is an Arabic term from the tri-literal root s-l-m (س، ل، م). It is derived from the word *ISTISLAM* which means to surrender or submission of desires to the will of *Allah* (SWT). The Muslims have to submit their will and desires before Almighty and at the same time fulfill their duties and obligations assigned to them by *Allah*(SWT). There are many duties to be fulfilled by a Muslim other than offering *salah*, *Zakat*, performing *Hajj* etc. One of the neglected duties assigned to man is, to take care of environment, to protect it and to conserve it. Environment protection is an important aspect of *Islam*. Being *Khalifah* or viceroy of *Allah* (SWT) on the Earth, Muslims are responsible to take care of the environment.

"It is He who has appointed you viceroys in the earth ... that He may try you in what He has given you."ⁱ

The environment has been adversely affected by human activities and man is responsible for the consequences of this immense devastation. The Qur'an has labelled this environmental devastation as *Fitnah* and held man responsible for this tragedy in following verses: ***"Corruption has appeared on earth and at sea because of what the hands of men have wrought; in order that God may make them taste the consequences of their action; so that they might return."***ⁱⁱ

Fitnah is not only linked with killings, chaos, testing and trial, misguidance, treachery, turbulence, and so on, but it is also related with changing the originality of things, which leads to disorder.ⁱⁱⁱ The Holy Quran is very clear on the subject of the environment. Through Qur'anic verses, Allah (SWT) has repeatedly advised humans not to disturb the peace of nature. Any attempt to upset the balance by poorly designed self-directed human activities will almost certainly overthrow the equilibrium and cause environmental concerns.^{iv}

The Islamic perspective on protection of environment reflects a positive image about *Islam* and how it embraces every single matter the humans face on earth as *Islam* is the multidimensional religion. In today's world, everyone talks about danger of war, over-population or pollution of air and water. But usually, the same people who discern these obvious problems speak of the necessity of further 'development', or war against 'human misery' stemming from conditions imposed by terrestrial existence itself. In other words, they wish to remove the problems brought by the destruction of the equilibrium between man and nature through further conquest and domination of nature. Few would be willing to admit that the acutest social and technical problems facing mankind today come not from so-called 'underdevelopment' but from 'over-development'. Few are willing to look reality in the face and accept the fact that there is no peace possible in human society as long as the attitude towards natural environment is one based on aggression and war.^v

Muslim Organizations and Environmental Conservation

There are many organizations that work on the principles laid by *Islam* to conserve and protect the environment. They can be listed as:

Green Muslims

During the month of Ramadan in 2007, a small group of Muslims organized a zero-waste potluck iftar. These individuals hoped to build an understanding of Muslim-based environmentalism that would spread across communities in order to promote awareness of global environmental challenges within a Muslim community. This group launched a debate on what distinctive measures Muslims could take to address local and spiritual environmental challenges. Within a few months, the group held two more green iftars, with attendance five times that of the first. Muslims in the Washington, DC region appeared to be anxiously awaiting this type of thought, and this group appeared to be filling the void. Since then, Green Muslims has continued to organize events to enhance environmental awareness and encourage environmental activism. It hosts educational programming for local youth, hosts community hikes and cleanups, and provides speakers and educational material for local Islamic centres and youth groups. They serve as a source in the *Muslim* community for spiritually-inspired environmental education, action, and reflection.^{vi}

Islamic Foundation for Ecology and Environmental Sciences

The Islamic Foundation for Ecology and Environmental Science (IFEES) is an environmental organization created in Birmingham, England in 1993 by Fazlun Khalid. The IFEES has created a variety of teaching tools to raise Muslims' knowledge of environmental issues, and is involved in numerous conservation and education projects throughout the *Muslim* world, including "green audits" for mosques and a "Sustainable Living" *Islam* summer camp. IFEES publishes a newsletter, *EcoIslam*, and has produced a film titled *Clean Medina*. The *Muslim Green Guide to Reducing Climate Change* was published by IFEES in 2008. In 2005 IFEES worked with CARE International to bring a halt to dynamite fishing in Zanzibar, and are currently conducting a tree-planting campaign in Indonesia called "Green Indonesia".^{vii}

They network world-wide and invite collaboration from organizations and individuals of all persuasions. Also, IFEES networks world-wide with NGOs, international organisations, academic bodies and grass roots organisations and invites collaboration from institutions and individuals from all persuasions who are also dedicated to the maintenance of the Earth as a healthy habitat for future generations of humankind as well as other sentient beings.^{viii}

Qur'anic Botanic Garden

An educational and practical program that introduces primary and high school students to the basics of botany, conservation and cultivation through field visits and practical and lab experiments. QBG has introduced a new concept in the world of botanical gardens, as it is the first garden of its kind in the world that exhibits the plants mentioned in the Holy Qur'an and the authentic Sunnah of the Prophet (PBUH). It aims to enhance and spread knowledge about these plants, the terms associated with them, and how they are cared for and preserved.

It is He who sends down rain from the sky; from it is drink and from it is foliage in which you pasture [animals]. He causes to grow for you thereby the crops, olives, palm trees, grapevines, and from all the fruits. Indeed in that is a sign for a people who give thought?^{ix}

QBG's vision is to be a world-class center of excellence for disseminating knowledge, education and research in the field of plant resources, and to extend bridges of communication between civilizations, contribute to enhancing responsibility towards the environment, and achieve integration between efforts to preserve plants and modern scientific achievements.^x In addition to its religious dimension, QBG also aims to shed light on the importance of preserving plant resources, how to conserve natural and environmental resources, and to highlight the teachings of Islamic law that call for the protection and preservation of environmental resources for current and future generations.^{xi}

Faith for Earth Initiative

Initiative launched in 2017, Faith for Earth has collaborated with representatives of more than 15 religions, highlighting how these faiths can mobilize the power of their followers and address some of the gravest threats to the planet. Along with organizing major conferences, they help religious leaders develop practical steps their followers can take to fight air pollution, protect biodiversity and limit plastic pollution. They also work with religious institutions, who are often major investors, to green their assets and reduce their environmental footprint.^{xii} Earlier this year, the Faith for Earth Initiative of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) launched a global push to bring together Islamic institutions from around the world in a bid to combat pollution, climate change and other threats to the planet. Called *Mizan*, Arabic for "balance", the charter is designed to showcase Islam's teachings on the environment and spur the world's 1.8 billion Muslims to embrace sustainability as part of their everyday lives.^{xiii}

Al-Mizan: A Covenant for the Earth

Al-Mizan presents an Islamic outlook of the environment in a bid to strengthen local, regional, and international actions that combat climate change and other threats to the planet. It is a global endeavour to engage Islamic scholars and *Muslim* institutions in the development and adoption of this Call. The global *Muslim* community is drafting its new environmental charter, titled *Al-Mizan: A Covenant for the Earth*. The draft was scheduled to be completed by late March 2021, with the final version published in October. Iyad Abumoghli, the Nairobi-based founding director of the United Nations Environment Programme's Faith for Earth project, announced the *Al-Mizan* endeavour last to last year.^{xiv}

Al-Mizan-A Covenant for the Earth is a restatement of the principles governing the protection of nature in a form that meets current challenges. It examines the ethics behind the social patterning of human existence and enquires into how they could be brought to life today working in harmony with the heartbeat of the natural world. Environmentalism is deeply embedded in the veins of *Islam*. It was based on the *Quran* and it could be distilled into three categories namely encouraging public good, forbidding wrong action and acting in moderation at all times^{xv}

“Let there be a community among you that calls for what is good, urges what is right and forbids what is wrong, they are the ones who have success”^{xvi}

AL-MIZAN (‘Balance’ in English) is based on *Surah Ar-Rahman* (The Merciful) in which *Allah* Almighty describes the creation in its perfect balance:^{xvii}

“The Most Merciful, Taught the Quran, Created Humankind, Taught him Eloquence, The sun and the moon move in precise calculation, and the stars and the trees prostrate, and the heaven He raised and imposed the balance (Mizan), That you not transgress within the balance (Mizan), and establish weight in justice and do not make deficient the balance (Mizan)”^{xviii}

Long-term hopes of *Mizan* include groundbreaking ideas. Bigger picture, they are ultimately hoping that more faith-based organizations will take *Mizan* as a guiding principle and mobilize action. *Mizan* aspires that they will also help foster an understanding between religions that we have a common responsibility towards the Earth.^{xix}

ISNA Green Initiative - Environmental Advocacy

The genesis of the Islamic Society of North America (ISNA) lay in the establishment of its predecessor organization, the Muslims Students Association of the United States and Canada (MSA). Sparked by the vision and determination of a dozen international *Muslim* students gathered on the campus of University of Illinois, Champaign-Urbana on January 1, 1963, MSA was founded and fuelled by limited resources but unbounded energy. The founding members of MSA met in a spirit of egalitarian partnership. They represented a great diversity of national, linguistic and even jurisprudential background among themselves. At the same time they shared a yearning for a future in which they and those who come after them will be torchbearers and practitioners of a way of life they had committed themselves to.^{xx}

Their aim was to be an exemplary and unifying Islamic organization in North America that contributes to the betterment of the *Muslim* community and society at large, to foster the development of the *Muslim* community, interfaith relations, civic engagement and better understanding of *Islam*.^{xxi}

Greening Our Ramadan

Scientific studies continuously draw attention to the perils of global warming. Paris Climate accord has been the recognition of the dire consequences, especially to the people in countries with little resources. In August 2015, *Muslim* scholars meeting in Istanbul issued “Islamic Declaration on Global Climate Change” which highlights the consequences of humanity’s massive exploitation of Earth. The declaration calls upon Muslims to tackle the habits, mindset and root causes of climate change, environmental degradation, and loss of biodiversity wherever they can in order to resolve these issues. Realizing the responsibility

towards the preservation and conservation of environment, ISNA in December 2014 established ISNA Green Initiative (Formerly known as Green *Masjid* Task Force) to create environmental awareness, guide mosques/Islamic centers towards environmentally friendly actions, and promote sustainable practices. Since 2015 ISNA Green Initiative have been conducting “Greening Our *Ramadan*” campaign to encourage environment friendly practices.

Wisdom in Nature

Wisdom in Nature formerly known as London Islamic Network for the Environment (LINE) was founded in UK by Muzammal Hussain in the 1990's. As one of a few Muslims who gave the occasional talk on Islamic ecology, and who was involved with local group activism in Brighton, he reflected on the possibility of starting local Islamic ecology groups in the UK as a way to join up those that had same sense of understanding and thinking. The first meeting of just three people took place on January 10th 2004 in his parents' home and with sustained effort the group became established. Eight months later on September 5th 2004, this new group decided on an official name: the London Islamic Network for the Environment, or LINE. The group held open monthly forums in central London with an inclusive circle format, reflecting on a range of themes; from Qur'anic reflections to 'Green Economics' from Peace activism to bio-fuels from Forum Theatre to Modern Social movements from Palestine to Food & farming and more. They also delivered numerous talks and workshops to a wide cross section of society and mobilized the *Muslim* Community to take action. They have often ended up in the role of pioneers and with no example in front of them designed and deliver what was probably the first course on *Islam* and Permaculture anywhere in the world, in 2010. Thus, weaving together Permaculture, Islamic ecology and Inclusive Leadership, allowed them to offer powerful training that is educational, fun, inspiring, and transformative. They have five strand activism model which is a “holistic framework for co-creating conscious, just, regenerative communities; and integrating land, people and economy.”^{xxii}

Conclusion

Considering the need and importance of natural environment, many past and present scientists and scholars have emphasized the value and importance of its conservation. Many Islamic scholars have also contributed considerably. In current scenario, earth is stressful as far as environmental degradation is concerned and to combat this situation, various summits are conducted locally and globally. We can say environmental conservation takes a central stage of all these discussions. *Islam* being a practice oriented religion, offers an opportunity for an effective environment friendly approach that will help in translating environmental protection theory into practical steps as the adherents to the Islamic faith will consider it as their religious duty and obligation. Looking around at the current state of environmental degradation and extent of negative impact due to climate change, one cannot but conclude that contemporary humanity has failed this test of being a Trustee on the earth. The world can no longer afford the cost of our failures. It is now the high time that people of all faiths unite and stand for a common cause for humanity.

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